

Data Management Plan

DMP Details

Title of the Center	TRANSITION – Center for Changing Urban and Rural Lives
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Project Overview

Funding Body	Grundforskningsfonden/Danish National Research Foundation
Grant Number / Project Acronym	TRANSITION – Center for Changing Urban & Rural Lives (DNRF 194)
Workzone Case Number	102-0039/24-4000
Principal Investigator	Pia Quist, Department of Nordic Studies and Linguistics
Project Members (including collaborators)	Medarbejdere i Grundforskningscenter TRANSITION/Staff at the TRANSITION – Center for Changing Urban and Rural Lives
Project Summary	<p>At TRANSITION – Centre for Changing Urban and Rural Lives, we explore how the transition from rural to urban-centric societies has shaped people's lived experiences throughout the 20th century. Researchers from the fields of history, literature and sociolinguistics collaborate to unravel this transition from a bottom-up perspective linking insights into the everyday lives of ordinary people to broader historical contexts, collective ideas, language and policies.</p> <p>At TRANSITION, we ask:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How have rural-urban transitions influenced people’s lived experiences? • How have these experiences shaped collective ideas, language, and practices? <p>Denmark’s unique archival resources—autobiographies, memoirs, diaries, dialect recordings, and literary texts—offer an exceptional foundation for studying how mobility, language, and cultural identity evolve over time. By combining qualitative and quantitative methods, we uncover new insights into transitions and their impact on people, places, and communities.</p> <p>Se: https://transition.ku.dk/ for mere info.</p>
Other Project Documentation	See attached research plan.

1. Data description

1.1 Describe what material and data will be collected, observed, generated, created or reused in the project. For the different types of research data, address their:

- Origin / Source
- Estimated size / Volume
- Expected format(s)

TRANSITION – Center for Changing Urban and Rural Lives builds its research on a wide array of qualitative source materials that document individual and collective experiences of rural–urban transitions in Denmark from the late 19th century to the present. These materials stem from public archives, institutional collections, and new data collection efforts initiated by researchers at the center.

The center works with data from a number of nationally significant collections, including NEU (Nationalmuseets Etnologiske Undersøgelser), NIHA (Nationalmuseets Industri-, Håndværker og Arbejdererindringer), and the Diary Collection/Dagbogindsamlingen, all hosted by the National Museum of Denmark; the collection of Danes’ written memories by the Municipal Archive of Copenhagen/Erindringsamlingen at Københavns Stadsarkiv; Link-Lives, a historical register dataset maintained by The Danish National Archives/Rigsarkivet; the Dialektarkiv and LANCHART corpus, both hosted at the University of Copenhagen; and literary corpora such as the MeMo corpus and the Corpus of Danish 20th and 21st Century Novels. In addition, TRANSITION will generate new research data through qualitative fieldwork and interviews during the grant period.

It is essential to emphasize that all original data remains under the custodianship of the respective archives and institutions. TRANSITION researchers work only with copies of selected material, obtained through formal access requests or institutional collaborations. These copies are used strictly for analytical purposes within the center and are stored securely on the University of Copenhagen’s institutional S-drive. Usage of the data is subject to the specific rules and restrictions set by the original data-holding institutions, including the National Museum of Denmark, the Danish National Archives, the Municipal Archive of Copenhagen, and internal UCPH data custodians.

The datasets comprise a variety of formats such as WAV or MP3 for audio recordings (e.g., dialect or interview data), PDF or TXT for textual materials (e.g., diaries, memoirs, transcripts), TIFF or JPEG for scanned visual materials, GIS for mappings, and CSV or Excel for structured metadata and administrative records. We estimate the total volume of data processed during the project to amount to between 3 and 5 terabytes.

1.2 Describe any material and data that contain sensitive information, including:

- Personal data
- Human biological material, including biobanks
- Classified information
- Confidential (business) information
- Any other material or data that must be protected to safeguard the security of individuals, organisms, communities, organisations, etc.

Many of the materials used in TRANSITION are historical in nature and concern individuals who are no longer alive. Nevertheless, several collections include personal data that must be handled in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This

includes both ordinary personal data (such as names, places of residence, or occupations) and, very rarely, sensitive data (e.g., information on health, religion, or political views).

The NEU, NIHA, Dagbogindsamlingen, LANCHART, and Dialektarkiv collections contain such data in varying formats, including diaries, interviews, and ethnographic reports. The Link-Lives dataset comprises linked register data on historical populations and includes identifiable information. In contrast, the MeMo corpus and other literary datasets contain fictional data with no privacy implications.

All newly collected data generated by TRANSITION researchers will be gathered with informed consent whenever possible or on the basis of scientific research purposes (forskningshjemmel), where required, and processed in accordance with the University of Copenhagen's data protection and ethical standards.

2. Right to research data

2.1 Address whether there are any access restrictions to material and data during the project. If so, describe who can have access to the material and data during the project, under which conditions, and in what timeframe.

The majority of the material used in TRANSITION concerns already existing data remaining under the ownership and custody of the institutions, which own and store that data and with own conditions for access, including possible restrictions on reuse, data sharing, and publication. TRANSITION researchers thus do not store or manage original datasets but work instead with digital or physical copies of selected materials provided for research purposes.

All TRANSITION research data is stored securely on the university's institutional S-drive. Access to this drive is limited to members of the TRANSITION research team and is controlled through KU's digital identity infrastructure. Individual access is granted only on a need-to-know basis and is regularly reviewed.

Researchers not affiliated with the center do not have direct access to TRANSITION research data unless this is explicitly permitted under the conditions set by the archive/collection which data originates from. However, TRANSITION researchers may collaborate with external partners in the analysis and interpretation of the material for research purposes, provided that data is used in line with these conditions. No third-party data is uploaded to shared or external platforms unless explicitly allowed, and all dissemination activities are planned with respect to the legal and ethical obligations agreed upon with the original data custodians.

2.2 Describe any material and data in the project that are subject to intellectual property rights.

The majority of the materials used in TRANSITION are obtained from public archives, institutional collections, or open literary corpora. As such, the intellectual property rights (IPR) associated with the data vary depending on the origin, type, and status of each source.

For historical and archival material — such as diaries, autobiographies, and ethnographic documentation accessed through the National Museum of Denmark, the Danish National Archives, the Municipal Archive of Copenhagen — copyright is typically held by the archive, the original author (if still protected), or has lapsed due to age. The center works

only with material it is legally entitled to access and use for research purposes under the terms set by the data providers. In many cases, such archival material is in the public domain or available under specific access conditions that do not confer ownership to the researcher or the institution using it.

Some of the datasets used in the center, particularly literary corpora such as the MeMo-corpus and the Corpus of Danish 20th and 21st Century Novels, may still be subject to copyright protections depending on the age and publication status of the texts. Where necessary, TRANSITION will comply with relevant copyright legislation, including limitations and exceptions for research and quotation. Where available, corpus materials that are out of copyright or licensed for academic use will be prioritized.

New empirical material collected by researchers affiliated with TRANSITION — such as interviews or field notes — will be generated as University of Copenhagen research projects and therefore fall under institutional IPR guidelines. Unless otherwise agreed, the university holds the rights to these data, although licensing for reuse (e.g., under Creative Commons terms) may be applied when participants have consented and when it is appropriate to do so.

The center does not claim ownership over third-party or archival material but ensures that its use of such data is compliant with applicable rights frameworks and respects the legal ownership retained by the source institutions or original authors.

2.3 List any agreements or contracts set up in the project that contain provisions on rights to material and data, such as research collaboration agreements, non-disclosure agreements, material transfer agreements or license agreements.

Grant Agreement with the Danish National Research Foundation (DNRF 194)

Collaboration Agreement the National Museum of Denmark

Data Agreement with the National Museum of Denmark

2.4 Describe any legislation, policies, guidelines or requirements that govern research data management in the project.

Research data management in TRANSITION is governed by a combination of institutional policies, national legislation, international regulation, and specific grant conditions. Together, these frameworks ensure that all data is handled securely, ethically, and in accordance with recognized standards for responsible research.

At the institutional level, the center adheres to the University of Copenhagen's Policy for Research Data Management (2022), which sets requirements for data planning, storage, access control, documentation, and long-term preservation. The UCPH Information Security Policy further governs the technical and organizational measures that apply to data security, including authentication, backup, and infrastructure management.

In relation to legal compliance, TRANSITION operates in accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Danish Data Protection Act, particularly where personal data concerning living individuals is involved. While the majority of data used in the center concerns deceased persons and historical material — and is thus not covered by GDPR — a thorough risk assessment has been completed, confirming that a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) is not required. Nevertheless, all data is handled with

a high level of ethical and legal diligence, including anonymization or pseudonymization where relevant.

TRANSITION is committed to working in line with the FAIR principles — ensuring that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable — as also required by the Danish National Research Foundation (DNRF). The center actively works to make its metadata openly available, uses standard formats and documentation practices, and shares data where legally and ethically possible, in accordance with the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary.”

Where data is obtained from archives and external institutions, including the National Museum of Denmark, the Danish National Archives, the Municipal Archive of Copenhagen, the center fully respects the specific access and reuse conditions set by each data provider. For newly collected material involving human participants, the University of Copenhagen’s ethical guidelines are followed, including obtaining informed consent whenever possible or on the basis of scientific research purposes (forskningshjemmel), whenever required, and ensuring secure handling of personally identifiable data.

2.5 Describe whether, when and how research data may be used for other purposes (e.g. other research projects) and what arrangements will be made if a project member leaves the project and/or UCPH before the end of the project.

Reuse of research data within TRANSITION is possible but always subject to the terms set by the original data providers and the legal or ethical constraints that apply to each dataset. TRANSITION researchers are responsible for ensuring that such reuse is legitimate and documented.

All newly collected data produced under the auspices of the center is stored centrally on UCPH’s infrastructure and documented with accompanying metadata. This ensures that such material can, where permitted, be reused in future research projects affiliated with the University of Copenhagen, provided that reuse aligns with the informed consent and ethical commitments made to participants when relevant.

If a project member leaves TRANSITION or UCPH before the project ends, their access to data stored on the S-drive is removed. Since all data remains centrally stored, no transfer is needed. Any relevant documentation is reviewed and updated by the project’s data manager or coordinator to ensure continued access for the research team. Former members may only reuse data if permitted under the original access agreements. Agreements for data transfer to other research institutions might be negotiated as long as these agreements respect the original terms of use for the research data in question.

3. Ethical and legal approvals

3.1 Describe any ethical considerations and approvals necessary for the collection, processing or use of material and data in the project. Ethical considerations might concern human rights and protection of human beings, animal protection and welfare, data protection and privacy, health and safety, environmental protection or artificial intelligence, for example.

Most of the material used in TRANSITION consists of historical, archival, or literary sources that do not involve living participants and are not subject to prior ethical approval. Where such material contains personal narratives or identifiable individuals, it is used in

accordance with the ethical access conditions set by the respective archives and with sensitivity to privacy and context.

In cases where TRANSITION collects new data — for example, through interviews or fieldwork — participation will be voluntary and based on informed consent whenever possible or based on scientific research purposes (forskningshjemmel) whenever required. Whenever possible, participants will be informed of the purpose of the research, their rights, and any planned use of quotes or data in publications. Likewise, consent will be documented in writing or via audio, and participants may review transcripts where relevant. Data will be stored securely and processed in compliance with GDPR and the Danish Data Protection Act, and registered in UCPH's record of research projects involving personal data.

Projects at TRANSITION do not involve animal research, environmental intervention, or artificial intelligence. Some data sets might involve health information but projects at TRANSITION do not have health data as their research object. Overall, the ethical risk profile is low, and projects at TRANSITION follow the guidelines of the Research Ethics Committee at the Faculty of Humanities.

3.2 Describe any legal agreements or approvals necessary for the collection and use of material and data in the project.

TRANSITION uses data from archives and collections with specific terms of use. All use of data is subject to the conditions set by these institutions, including restrictions on reuse and dissemination, and governed by applicable legislation.

The center works only with copies of original material and does not claim ownership of externally sourced data. Researchers are responsible for ensuring compliance with archive-specific terms.

For new data collected by TRANSITION, informed consent will be obtained whenever possible or be based on scientific research purposes (forskningshjemmel) whenever required, and data will be processed in accordance with GDPR and the Danish Data Protection Act. Such projects will be registered in UCPH's joint record of research involving personal data. No additional legal approvals are required for the planned research activities.

4. Collection, processing and documentation

4.1 Indicate what methods will be employed in the project to ensure the consistency and quality of the material and data.

This Data Management Plan defines the overall framework for how data is to be handled in research projects affiliated with TRANSITION. Projects at the center work with a broad range of data types, including diaries, autobiographies, ethnographic notes, dialect recordings, interviews, and literary texts, primarily accessed through public archives and institutional collections as detailed in the research plan and the associated archive overview.

Each individual project is responsible for preparing its own Data Management Plan, whether it involves new data collection or the reuse of existing material. All projects must follow UCPH's Policy for Research Data Management, the Information Security Policy, and relevant legal and ethical requirements, including the GDPR and the guidelines of the Research Ethics Committee at the Faculty of Humanities.

New data must be securely stored on UCPH infrastructure, documented with appropriate metadata, and, where applicable, registered in UCPH's joint record of research projects involving personal data. Reuse of existing data must comply with the access terms and conditions set by the original data providers.

4.2 Describe how the material and data will be organized and structured.

Projects affiliated with TRANSITION are expected to structure their data in a way that ensures clarity, transparency, and consistency throughout the research process. This includes using logical folder structures, descriptive file naming conventions, and clear separation between raw data, processed data, and documentation.

Data should be organized by source or collection, and where relevant, by date, data type, or project sub-theme. Naming conventions should reflect identifiable elements such as archive or location, and versioning must be applied consistently across files and datasets.

Each project is responsible for maintaining documentation (e.g. README files, metadata records) that explains how data is structured, what each folder or file contains, and how the data connects to the project's research questions or outputs. Where personal data is involved, projects must ensure that data is either anonymized, and that file or folder names do not contain directly identifying information. This is essential to meeting GDPR obligations and protecting the privacy of data subjects.

The center encourages the use of standardized folder and file organization practices, while allowing flexibility to accommodate disciplinary norms and the nature of the material used.

4.3 Describe how the collection, processing and analysis of the material and data will be documented.

Each project affiliated with TRANSITION is responsible for documenting how its data is collected, processed, and analyzed in a transparent and reproducible manner. This includes written descriptions of data sources, selection criteria, digitization or transcription processes (if relevant), and the analytical procedures applied.

Documentation should be maintained in the form of README files, methodological notes, or data processing logs, and stored alongside the data itself on UCPH's secure infrastructure. For reused archival material, projects must clearly record the origin of the data, the terms of access, and any transformation or selection applied before use.

When new data is collected, documentation must include information on consent procedures (if relevant), anonymization steps, and any coding or indexing applied during analysis. This may also include analytical memos, field notes, or summaries of coding frameworks.

All documentation must be written in a way that allows other researchers within the center (or, where relevant, outside it) to understand and verify how the data was handled. This supports both internal transparency and the long-term reusability of research data.

4.4 Describe what the approach will be for naming and versioning of data files and material.

Projects affiliated with TRANSITION are expected to apply consistent and descriptive naming conventions for all data files and associated material. File names should clearly

indicate relevant attributes such as the data source, date, document type, version number, or project code. File names must not include directly identifying personal information.

Versioning should be applied systematically throughout the data lifecycle. Each version of a file should be clearly marked using standard suffixes (e.g. _v01, _v02, _final), and earlier versions should be retained or archived in accordance with the project's documentation strategy. A version history log or changelog may be used to track updates or edits to data files, particularly in projects involving transcription, annotation, or iterative coding.

Projects are encouraged to use folder-level organization to distinguish between raw data, processed data, and analysis outputs, and to reflect these distinctions in file naming. This ensures that data remains traceable and that collaborators or future users can easily identify the most current version of any given file.

4.5 Indicate what metadata will be associated with the material and data.

All projects within TRANSITION must create and maintain metadata that documents the origin, structure, and content of their research data. Metadata should include key information such as the title and description of the dataset, creator(s), date of creation, data format, language, access conditions, license, and keywords. Where applicable, references to original archival sources or access agreements should also be included.

Projects are encouraged to use established metadata standards where feasible, such as Dublin Core, and to maintain metadata files in open formats like CSV, TXT, or XML. Each dataset should be accompanied by a README file that explains the structure and variables of the data, as well as any relevant processing steps, consent conditions, or analytical frameworks.

Metadata should be stored alongside the data on UCPH's infrastructure and updated throughout the research process. Where data will be deposited in a repository (e.g. UCPH Dataverse or Zenodo), metadata must meet the requirements of that platform to support findability, access, and reuse in line with the FAIR principles.

5. Storage and information security

5.1 Describe where and how the material and data will be stored and backed up during the project.

All data used in research projects at TRANSITION is stored on the University of Copenhagen's secure S-drive infrastructure. Researchers at the center work exclusively with copies of material obtained from archives, collections, or data providers; the original data remains under the custody and storage responsibility of the institutions that own it.

The S-drive provides secure storage with automatic daily backup, institutional redundancy, and restricted access based on KU login credentials. Access is limited to relevant project members and is reviewed periodically to ensure data security and compliance with internal policies.

No research data is stored on personal devices or external platforms. All storage follows the University's Information Security Policy and ensures that data remains protected against accidental loss, unauthorized access, or corruption.

5.2 Describe how the material and data will be shared with collaborators during the project (if any).

Collaboration is central to the research conducted within TRANSITION, and data may be shared with internal or external collaborators as part of ongoing or future projects. Since the specific form of collaboration may vary — from co-authorship to joint analysis or comparative studies — no fixed data-sharing model applies across all projects.

Regardless of collaboration type, all sharing of data must comply with the access conditions set by the original data providers, as well as relevant legislation (including GDPR), UCPH's Information Security Policy, and the individual project's Data Management Plan. Copies of archival or restricted material may only be shared if permitted under the original access agreement, and any personal data must be anonymized before external sharing unless other safeguards are in place.

When data is shared outside UCPH, secure transfer methods must be used approved by the University. Collaborators must be informed of applicable data handling responsibilities, including confidentiality and reuse restrictions.

5.3 For projects in which personal data are processed (including biobanks), please indicate whether a GDPR risk assessment and Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) have been carried out.

A GDPR risk assessment has been carried out for TRANSITION. Based on the nature of the data — which consists mainly of historical and archival materials, often concerning deceased individuals — the assessment concluded that the risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects is low.

As a result, a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) is not required under current GDPR guidelines. The assessment has been documented and is available upon request.

Individual projects within the center that process personal data — particularly data collected from living individuals — must conduct their own GDPR risk assessments and, if necessary, DPIAs in accordance with UCPH procedures. All such projects must register in the joint UCPH record of research involving personal data and ensure that processing complies with GDPR and the Danish Data Protection Act.

5.4 For all research data types, describe what security measures will be established to prevent breaches of confidentiality. How will unauthorized access be prevented?

All data used in TRANSITION is stored on the University of Copenhagen's secure S-drive, which is protected by institutional access controls. Access to project folders is restricted to authorized team members and managed through KU's central identity system. Only researchers who are directly involved in a given project are granted access, and access rights are reviewed regularly to ensure that only current, relevant personnel can view or edit data.

Unauthorized access is prevented through a combination of technical and organizational measures, including password-protected logins (via KU NetID), role-based access control, and two-factor authentication (where applicable). The S-drive is hosted on protected servers managed by UCPH IT, with physical and digital safeguards in place.

Researchers are instructed not to store data locally or on personal devices, and confidential data must never be transferred via unsecured channels. Any data sharing outside UCPH must follow secure transfer protocols and only take place when permitted under the relevant data use agreements.

These measures ensure that confidentiality is maintained and that data is protected against unauthorized access, in accordance with UCPH's Information Security Policy and applicable data protection legislation.

5.5 For all research data types, describe what security measures will be established to prevent loss of integrity. How will data and material be safeguarded against loss or modifications?

To ensure the integrity of research data, all materials used in TRANSITION are stored on the University of Copenhagen's S-drive, which includes daily automated backups, access logging, and protection against unauthorized modification. The S-drive infrastructure is managed centrally by UCPH IT and includes built-in safeguards to detect and prevent data corruption or accidental loss.

Original data from external archives and collections is never modified by the center. Copies used for analysis are stored separately from derived or processed versions, and versioning is applied systematically to maintain a clear history of changes. Projects are expected to document all transformations, edits, or annotations in accompanying logs or metadata files.

Researchers do not have administrative rights over shared storage, which further limits the risk of accidental or unauthorized alteration of files. In cases where data must be edited — for example, in transcription or coding workflows — a copy of the original file is retained in a read-only format to preserve its unaltered state.

These measures ensure that data remains authentic, traceable, and verifiable throughout its lifecycle, in line with UCPH's Information Security Policy and research data management standards.

5.6 For all research data types, describe what security measures will be established to prevent reduced data availability. How will the continued accessibility of data and material to the relevant project members be assured?

All research data used in TRANSITION is stored on the University of Copenhagen's S-drive, which ensures high availability and institutional continuity. The S-drive is maintained by UCPH IT and includes automatic daily backups, version history, and redundancy measures to prevent data loss due to hardware failure or accidental deletion.

Access to project data is managed centrally through KU's digital identity infrastructure. As long as researchers are affiliated with the university and a given project, their access can be maintained or adapted as needed. In the event of staff changes, the center's coordinator and relevant project leads are responsible for updating access rights to ensure uninterrupted availability to the rest of the research team.

All projects are expected to document the location and structure of their data clearly (see Section 4.2), making it possible for authorized colleagues to locate and use data even if a key person is unavailable. Where applicable, access to critical documentation and metadata is shared with more than one team member to prevent bottlenecks.

These measures ensure that data remains accessible to the right people throughout the research process, in accordance with UCPH's Information Security Policy and best practices for collaborative research.

6. Data sharing

6.1 Describe which material and data will be made openly available for reuse.

Projects affiliated with TRANSITION are encouraged to make research data openly available for reuse where legally and ethically possible, in line with the FAIR principles and the center's commitment to responsible and transparent research.

In general, metadata, documentation, and datasets that are fully anonymized or derived from public domain sources — such as selected literary texts, transcribed interviews with consent for reuse, or analytical datasets based on archival material — may be made openly available. Examples include processed versions of data from the MeMo-corpus, published historical texts, or aggregated content analyses.

The availability of reused archival data depends on the conditions set by the original data holders. Where those conditions permit, and where no personal or sensitive data is present, copies or derivatives of such material may be shared in open repositories. Otherwise, metadata and methodological documentation can still be shared to support transparency and citation, even when the underlying data cannot be made publicly available.

All projects must assess the legal and ethical implications of data sharing on a case-by-case basis and include relevant decisions in their individual Data Management Plans.

6.2 Are there any material or data that cannot be shared openly? Explain why.

Some of the material used in projects affiliated with TRANSITION cannot be made openly available due to legal, ethical, or contractual restrictions. In particular, data accessed from archives, museums, or institutional collections is often subject to terms of use that prohibit public redistribution or reuse beyond the approved research context.

In other cases, data may contain personal or sensitive information, or be linked to individuals in ways that make full anonymization difficult. Even if data concerns historical subjects, contextual sensitivity or the risk of re-identification may still limit its shareability.

These limitations are assessed on a case-by-case basis and documented in the individual project's Data Management Plan. When data cannot be shared, projects are still encouraged to make metadata, documentation, and research outputs openly available to support transparency and scholarly exchange.

6.3 Describe any agreements required for sharing material and data (e.g. data processing agreements and material transfer agreements, if applicable).

When material or data is shared beyond the immediate research team, appropriate agreements must be in place to define the terms of access, use, and responsibilities. These may include material transfer agreements (MTAs), data processing agreements (DPAs), or collaboration contracts, depending on the nature of the data and the institutional roles of those involved.

For data sourced from external archives or institutions, sharing is only permitted if explicitly allowed under the original access conditions. In such cases, additional agreements may be required to clarify how data may be reused, cited, or further distributed.

If personal data is shared with external collaborators, a data processing agreement must be established in accordance with the GDPR and UCPH's data protection procedures. All data sharing must follow secure transmission protocols and be documented appropriately.

Each project is responsible for identifying the need for such agreements and ensuring that they are signed and stored before any data is transferred.

Making research data FAIR

6.4 *Findable*: What metadata will be created to allow the discovery of the material and data? How will others be able to discover the metadata?

All projects within TRANSITION are expected to create metadata that enables others to discover and understand the existence and purpose of their datasets, even if the underlying data is not openly accessible. Metadata will describe the dataset's content, origin, structure, licensing conditions, and any access restrictions, and will be written in English to support international visibility.

Metadata will be deposited in a suitable repository that supports long-term accessibility and complies with recognized standards for persistent identification and indexing. The chosen repository must allow metadata to be indexed by search engines and academic registries to support findability in accordance with the FAIR principles.

Standard metadata formats will be used where appropriate, and projects are encouraged to apply relevant keywords and subject classifications to enhance discoverability.

6.5 *Findable*: Will the material and data receive persistent identifiers?

To support long-term findability and citation, all datasets and metadata records produced within projects affiliated with TRANSITION should be assigned persistent identifiers (PIDs), such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). These identifiers make it possible to reference datasets unambiguously in publications, documentation, and repositories.

The use of persistent identifiers will be implemented through the chosen data repository, which must support automatic or manual DOI registration. Where relevant, identifiers may also be assigned to specific versions of datasets or to related outputs such as codebooks or documentation files.

Projects are responsible for ensuring that the metadata associated with each PID remains accurate and up to date, and for linking the identifier to any relevant publications, documentation, or access conditions.

6.6 *Accessible*: Where will the material and data be deposited (e.g. in which repository)? How will others be able to access and retrieve the material and data?

Projects affiliated with TRANSITION will deposit data and metadata in a repository that supports long-term preservation, persistent identifiers, and compliance with FAIR principles. The selected repository must allow for metadata publication and, where appropriate, restricted or open access to data.

Although no specific repository has been chosen at this point, the center ensures that all data and metadata are prepared and documented in a way that enables later deposit. Repositories used must meet standards for reliability, sustainability, and accessibility.

6.7 *Accessible*: Will there be any conditions or restrictions for access to the material and data?

Access to material and data from projects affiliated with TRANSITION will depend on the legal, ethical, and contractual conditions attached to each dataset. Some data may be made openly available, while other material — particularly that obtained from archives or containing personal information — may be subject to access restrictions.

When data cannot be shared publicly, access may be granted on request under specific conditions, such as research-purpose-only use, citation obligations, or approval from the original data provider. These conditions must be clearly stated in the accompanying metadata and documentation.

All access must be managed in compliance with applicable legislation (including GDPR), institutional policies, and the terms set by original data holders. Projects are responsible for defining and documenting any access conditions in their individual Data Management Plans.

6.8 *Interoperable*: Will digital data be shared in file formats that others can easily open and reuse? Will information be provided on how files can be read and processed?

Projects affiliated with TRANSITION are expected to use open and widely supported file formats to ensure that digital data can be accessed, read, and reused by others. Preferred formats include formats such as TXT, CSV, PDF/A, XML, WAV, and JPEG/TIFF, depending on the data type.

Where proprietary formats are used during analysis or collection (e.g. DOCX, XLSX, NVivo files), a non-proprietary version should be provided for sharing and preservation when feasible.

Documentation must accompany the data to explain how files are structured and how they can be interpreted or processed. This includes file descriptions in README files, metadata records, and any necessary encoding or software information needed to understand the dataset.

These practices support long-term usability and align with the FAIR principles of data interoperability.

6.9 *Interoperable*: Will standards for metadata (including vocabularies and ontologies) be applied?

Projects within TRANSITION are expected to apply established metadata standards to support interoperability and long-term usability. Where appropriate, standards such as Dublin Core will be used to ensure consistency in describing datasets, including fields for title, creator, date, format, subject, license, and access conditions.

Controlled vocabularies or classification systems may be applied where relevant to enhance searchability and integration with repository indexing systems. All metadata must be written in English and use consistent terminology to support international discoverability.

Projects are responsible for selecting appropriate standards based on their data type and repository requirements, and for documenting any deviations where necessary.

6.10 *Reusable*: What documentation is required for others to understand the material and data? How is this documentation provided?

Projects affiliated with TRANSITION must provide sufficient documentation to ensure that their data can be understood, interpreted, and reused by others. This includes README files, methodological notes, and metadata that explain the context of the data, how it was collected or derived, its structure, any processing steps, and any relevant coding schemes or analytical frameworks.

Documentation should accompany the data and be stored in accessible formats such as TXT, PDF, or CSV. All documentation must be written in English and clearly linked to the relevant datasets.

Where appropriate, projects may also include information about the consent conditions under which data was collected, as well as guidance on any limitations to reuse. This ensures transparency and supports responsible and informed secondary use of the material.

6.11 *Reusable*: Are there any conditions for the reuse of the material and data by others? How are these conditions communicated? Will you apply standard usage licenses?

Conditions for the reuse of material and data in TRANSITION projects depend on the legal status of the data and the terms set by the original data providers. Where possible, data and documentation will be made available under standard licenses, such as Creative Commons licenses (e.g. CC-BY or CC-BY-NC), to support clarity and reuse.

For material that cannot be openly shared — for example, due to archive restrictions or privacy concerns — reuse may be limited or subject to case-by-case approval. These conditions must be clearly described in the metadata and accompanying documentation.

Each project is responsible for determining and applying appropriate usage licenses to its data and for communicating any limitations on reuse through metadata fields, README files, or repository settings. Where applicable, citation requirements, attribution terms, and reuse conditions must be made explicit.

This approach ensures that data is reused responsibly and in accordance with legal, ethical, and contractual obligations.

7. Long term preservation

7.1 Describe which material and data will be preserved after project end. Note that:

- Unless regulated otherwise, research data underlying published results must be retained for at least five years.
- Research projects that fall within the scope of the *Executive Order No.514 (20/04/2020) on the Reporting of Digital Research Data Generated by State Authorities* must register information about the project and/or data with the Danish National Archives. Data from these projects may not be discarded or destroyed, and must therefore be preserved, unless or until the Danish National Archives issue a disposal provision.

All research projects affiliated with TRANSITION are responsible for ensuring that relevant research data is preserved after project completion. As a general rule, data underlying published results must be retained for at least five years, unless a longer retention period is required by law, funder policy, or data provider agreements.

Projects must assess which data has long-term value and ensure that it is preserved in a sustainable and accessible format. This includes curated datasets, metadata, documentation, and codebooks necessary to verify or reproduce published findings.

If a project falls under Executive Order No. 514 of 20 April 2020 on the reporting and preservation of digital research data generated by state authorities, the project must register its data with the Danish National Archives and comply with the archive's guidance on

preservation. In such cases, data may not be discarded or destroyed without a disposal provision from the Archives.

Data that cannot be legally or ethically preserved — for example, due to consent limitations or archive-imposed restrictions — must be documented accordingly. Each project must include its preservation strategy in its individual Data Management Plan.

7.2 Describe how the material and data will be preserved after project end:

Where will the material and data be stored? In which formats? For how long? What documentation and metadata will be associated?

As a minimum, describe how (a copy of) the digital data and corresponding documentation will be made available to research managers and/or supervisors at UCPH.

After project completion, research data and associated documentation from projects affiliated with TRANSITION must be preserved in a form that ensures future accessibility, traceability, and compliance with legal and institutional requirements.

Digital data to be preserved must be stored either in a trusted repository or on long-term institutional infrastructure that meets standards for research data preservation. Preferred formats for preservation include formats such as PDF/A, CSV, TXT, TIFF, JPEG, and WAV, as these are open, non-proprietary, and suitable for long-term access.

Metadata and documentation — including README files, consent statements (if applicable), and processing notes — must accompany the preserved data to ensure that others can understand and reuse it. All documentation should be stored in English and linked to the relevant datasets.

As a minimum requirement, a copy of the preserved data and documentation must be made available to research managers or supervisors at UCPH. This may be done via continued access to UCPH's institutional storage (e.g. the S-drive) or by deposit in an approved repository. Researchers are responsible for ensuring that access arrangements are in place prior to project closure.

For projects covered by Executive Order No. 514, data must be preserved in accordance with the requirements of the Danish National Archives and registered through their reporting system.

7.3 Indicate who will have access to the material and data after project end.

After the conclusion of a project affiliated with TRANSITION, access to preserved data and documentation must be ensured for relevant stakeholders at the University of Copenhagen. This includes the project's principal investigator, co-researchers (as appropriate), and the center's leadership or data management coordinator, where relevant.

If data is stored in a repository, access will be managed through the repository's access control settings and license terms. For data retained on UCPH's institutional infrastructure (e.g. the S-drive), continued access must be arranged in advance, and responsibility for managing access must be clearly delegated.

Any personal data or restricted material must remain protected under applicable legal and contractual conditions. No access may be granted to external parties without proper authorization or new agreements.

Responsibility for maintaining or transferring access lies with the project's principal investigator, who must ensure that data is neither abandoned nor made inaccessible when team members leave the university or the project concludes.

8. Resources and Responsibilities

8.1 Describe what costs are associated with the management of material data during the project. How will these costs be covered?

There are no direct project-level costs associated with data management in TRANSITION beyond those covered by institutional overhead. Data storage and security are handled through the University of Copenhagen's central IT infrastructure, which is funded via overhead and not charged to the project budget.

The center is not responsible for managing or preserving the original data, as most material is accessed from external archives and collections. These are owned and maintained by the institutions that hold them, and any costs related to long-term preservation, digitization, or technical infrastructure are borne by those institutions.

The only direct cost covered by the center's grant is a 25% position for an archive specialist at the National Museum of Denmark. This role supports the center by facilitating access to relevant archival materials but does not involve direct responsibility for technical data management.

All other data management tasks — including documentation, metadata, and regulatory compliance — are carried out by researchers within the scope of their regular responsibilities.

8.2 Describe what costs are associated with the preservation of material and data after the project (according to the preservation plan and retention period outlined in question 7.2)?? How will these costs be covered?

TRANSITION does not cover data preservation costs directly. Long-term preservation of data is handled either through UCPH's institutional infrastructure, which is funded via overhead, or through external repositories that provide preservation services without charge for basic use.

Original data accessed from external archives and collections remains the responsibility of the institutions that own it, including any costs related to its long-term maintenance. The center only works with copies of such material and does not assume preservation responsibilities or associated expenses for the originals.

Preservation of data generated within the center will follow the strategy outlined in this Data Management Plan and will rely on institutional support and available infrastructure.

8.3 Indicate who will carry out the different tasks for managing the material and data during the project, and for long term preservation.

Responsibility for managing data during the project lies with the researchers leading individual projects affiliated with TRANSITION. This includes organizing, documenting, storing, and—where applicable—processing or collecting data in compliance with legal and ethical requirements.

Each project is responsible for preparing its own Data Management Plan within the framework established by this center-level plan. Researchers must ensure that data is stored on UCPH's secure infrastructure, that metadata and documentation are maintained, and that any reuse or sharing follows applicable conditions.

The center coordinator and relevant administrative staff may support data management activities by facilitating access to infrastructure, coordinating compliance with institutional policies, and providing guidance on documentation or repository use.

Responsibility for long-term preservation also rests with the individual project teams, who must ensure that data and documentation are preserved appropriately before the end of the project. Where required, supervisors or principal investigators must arrange continued access and ensure that datasets are either retained within UCPH's infrastructure or deposited in an appropriate repository.

8.4 Indicate who will be the main person(s) responsible during and after the project for:

- Allocating costs and resources.
- Obtaining approvals and ethical assessments.
- Meeting legal and contractual obligations.
- Controlling access to material and data.
- Maintaining the integrity and availability of published and preserved material and data.

Within TRANSITION, overall responsibility for data management lies with the researcher in charge of individual research projects, supported by relevant UCPH administrative units. Responsibilities are distributed as follows:

Allocating costs and resources: This is overseen by the Director of the Center and the center coordinator, in accordance with the funding from the Danish National Research Foundation and UCPH's internal support structures.

Obtaining approvals and ethical assessments: Individual project leaders are responsible for obtaining necessary ethical approvals or internal registrations, including registration in UCPH's record of research involving personal data and, where relevant, adherence to the guidelines of the Research Ethics Committee at the Faculty of Humanities.

Meeting legal and contractual obligations: Compliance with data protection law (GDPR and the Danish Data Protection Act), archival agreements, and institutional policies is the responsibility of each project leader, with guidance from UCPH's relevant administrative units.

Controlling access to material and data: Project leaders are responsible for ensuring that access to project data is appropriately restricted to authorized personnel and managed through UCPH's secure infrastructure (e.g. the S-drive). The center coordinator may support access management across projects where needed.

Maintaining the integrity and availability of published and preserved material and data: Each project leader must ensure that data is preserved in a trustworthy form, documented appropriately, and remains accessible to relevant stakeholders after the project's conclusion. The use of institutional storage or repositories must be planned and documented accordingly.